

AESTHETIC-ETHICAL APPROACH

Abstract | Taking into consideration Immanuel Wallerstein's prognosis of the current state of the world-system on one hand, and complex, diluted contemporary cultural arrangements on the other hand, the question of the next step arises - what is the next possible concept(s) that would bring about the necessary cultural change?

The paper shows, through thorough analysis and comparison of seemingly incompatible texts that such a concept can be found through art. What is more, this concept, the aesthetic-ethical approach, is the need, as Erich Fromm would say, that stems from the nature of man, making the concept universal no matter its different particular applications.

In short, the paper:

1. Introduces and presents the views of Friedrich Schiller, Arthur Schopenhauer and the evolutionary aesthetics on art and human nature.
2. Compares above presented views with the presented views and ideas of the aesthetics of everyday life, especially the dichotomy between routine and charisma.
3. Emphasizes the need for a permanent, deliberate interplay between routine and charisma, thus creating charismatic-routine and routine-charisma.
4. Creates an argument for an aesthetic-ethical approach, which is a direct answer to the above stated question of the next step.

Index terms | *art; beauty; change; charisma; human nature; routine; sublime.*

INTRODUCTION

World-systems analysis shows that “systems have lives. They come into existence at some point in time and space, for reasons and in ways that we can analyze”¹, but they also experience crisis and bifurcate, something that is now happening to the modern world-system. Immanuel Wallerstein says that the “crisis [of the modern world-system] may go on another twenty-five to fifty years”² and it is in this time that “a new order will emerge (...), and that this new order will be shaped as a function of what everyone does in the interval”³. The question that arises is thus: Which concept is the concept that can lead to the change in contemporary society?

What this paper shows, through thorough analysis and comparison of seemingly incompatible texts, is that such concept can be found through art. What is more, this concept, *aesthetic-ethical approach*, is the need, as Erich Fromm says in his book *The Sane Society*, that stems from the nature of man.

In short, the paper:

1. Introduces and presents the views of Friedrich Schiller, Arthur Schopenhauer and evolutionary aesthetics on art and human nature.
2. Compares above-mentioned views with the presented views and ideas of everyday aesthetics, especially the dichotomy between routine and charisma.
3. Emphasizes the need for permanent, deliberate interplay between routine and charisma.
4. Creates an argument for *aesthetic-ethical approach* – a direct answer to the above stated question.

The dichotomy of human nature and play drive

Friedrich Schiller’s book *On the Aesthetic Education of Man* deals with art and its role in society. The work is especially interesting, because it does not only talk about the art’s necessity in our life, but also points out the difference aesthetic approach to life can make.

At the time when Schiller wrote his letters and developed his view on art, the situation of the society was very similar to the one today – it was in the need of change. However, although Schiller’s interest, the state of the society of the time, and his arguments about art’s importance are very similar to the ideas that build this paper, there is a fundamental difference in the approach taken.

Yes, Schiller, precisely because of his concern for the society, and especially because of its extremely bad condition, sees art as a solution to the question of nature, culture and

freedom of man. Yes, he sees art as a medium of progress, of both humankind in general and each individual separately, but he bases such conclusions on a predetermined dichotomy of human nature.

Schiller, arising from the consequences of the French Revolution, concludes that there is more than an obvious imbalance between reason and sentiment, resulting in the lack of moral possibility and slow but sure collapse of society. The answer to this imbalance can be found in art, more specifically, play drive.

According to Schiller, there are two fundamental drives – sense and form drive. These two opposing drives never meet. Because of this, the imbalance often arises, resulting in domination of one drive. To overcome this, a third drive, the drive that unites in balance otherwise imbalanced dichotomy, has to be introduced – play drive.

By doing so, Schiller emphasizes art's important and crucial role in gaining knowledge and influencing social change. The knowledge that art (play drive) gives us is an insight into the pure concept of humanity, because only with play drive's effect can we realize our highest potential and adequate societal change can take place.

Escaping the Will – beautiful and sublime

In his work, *The World as Will and Representation*, Arthur Schopenhauer develops his philosophy of the Will. To him, the Will is the source of everything that exists, of nature, of individuals, and of suffering. This suffering can be stopped, although only for a moment, by becoming a pure will-less subject through aesthetic contemplation.

However, if stopping of the suffering through aesthetic contemplation is far from universal or permanent nature, the question that arises is – is there a way to stop the suffering for a longer period, if not permanently? The possible answer to this lies in the difference between beautiful and sublime – two versions of aesthetic contemplation.

Beautiful has a very special, easy attitude towards knowledge. Through beautiful, through its contemplation, we naturally and unconsciously escape the Will and stop the suffering. But such stopping is only temporary. In certain cases, it is so short that it goes by unnoticed. Therefore, stopping of the suffering for a longer period only by the means of beautiful would be impossible.

On the other hand, sublime does not have an easy attitude towards knowledge. Far from it. The relationship sublime has towards knowledge is one of a more targeted, persistent repetition of the lessons learned from the easy attitude of beautiful towards knowledge. It is conscious stopping of the suffering, and as such has to be maintained. Only by conscious maintenance of sublime state and the pure knowledge associated

with it, can we escape the Will and stop the suffering for a longer period.

Evolutionary aesthetics and spontaneous-general-knowledge

Taking into account the long history of art-knowledge-human nature trinity, the rise in tendency to gain certain knowledge through art does not surprise. The knowledge we get comes in all shapes and sizes. Fiction, as Denis Dutton mentions in his book *The Art Instinct*, is one of them. Through fiction, that is, through art, we get an interesting and detailed knowledge of how it is to be someone else. We are immersed in various roles, we feel different emotions, and consequently gain certain knowledge. It could be said that art shapes and teaches us without directly putting us in danger.

Of course, the knowledge we gain from art is mostly either sought-after-knowledge or spontaneous-individual-knowledge. The exception is spontaneous-general-knowledge about human nature we gain through evolutionary aesthetics without even seeking it.

For example, Dutton is interested in where beauty comes from and how it is that we can trace the universality of beauty and art throughout such a wide range of different cultures. Through the process of seeking this knowledge, Dutton not only gains sought-after-knowledge about why universalism arises in art, but also spontaneous-general-knowledge about human nature.

Precisely this opposite approach to one taken by Shiller and even Schopenhauer, focusing on the question of art and not human nature, is essential to evolutionary aesthetics. It is this approach that enables us to gain knowledge about human nature through art. Without art and its questions, innate and inseparable nature of beauty in relation to human nature would not be discovered.

Everydayness vs. non-everyday-like

In her book, *Everyday Aesthetics*, Katya Mandoki explores how different everyday cultural practices constitute play, and advocates the importance of extending aesthetics into the field of everyday life, and she is not alone in her endeavor. In her book, *Everyday Aesthetics*, Yuriko Saito studies our daily aesthetic experiences and their strong impact on the state of the world and quality of our life. She discusses the inadequacy of aesthetics focused on art, the aesthetic evaluation of the distinctive signs of objects or phenomena, responses to various manifestations of transience and aesthetic expression of moral values, and she examines the moral, political, existential and environmental consequences of these and other issues.

Yet, unlike Mandoki and Saito, in his article "What is 'Everyday' in Everyday Aesthetics?", Ossi Naukkarinen is primarily interested in what is everyday, and not so much in expanding the field of aesthetics from the study of art and beauty to other areas, one being everyday life. It is thus not surprising that for Naukkarinen everyday life is

“the unavoidable basis on which everything else is built. Life without everydayness is practically impossible, and it is difficult to even imagine a life that would be completely non-everyday-like”⁴.

Later in the article, he develops his scheme and highlights routine and non-routine, or everydayness and non-everyday-like in our lives, and gives art as an example of a positive interruption of routine, surpassing of the typical. However, he does point out that while art works can produce extraordinary experiences in certain people, they are something completely known, everyday-like, to others. He thus concludes that “everyday aesthetics cannot be defined by saying that it is the aesthetics of non-art (or non-nature), or that art-related aesthetics is necessarily something that is unsuited for the everyday contexts”⁵.

It is obvious that Naukkarinen tackles the question of defining everyday aesthetics in his own way and says that “art and art-relatedness can be an essential part of one’s everyday life”⁶ and that “there is no single best definition of what the aesthetic is; instead, there are several intertwining interpretations”⁷ all of them relevant to everyday aesthetics. However, what is interesting to us, more than Naukkarinen’s view on defining everyday aesthetics, are two concepts that reappear repeatedly – routine and non-routine, or as Weber would say, charisma.

Our everyday life consists of routine things, patterns that repeat themselves from day to day. But our life also consists of charismatic moments - events, things that act as an interruption of routine. Such interruptions can be planned or they just happen. In any case, they change our everyday life.

ArtoHaapala, in his article “On the Aesthetics of the Everyday: Familiarity, Strangeness, and the Meaning of Place”, tackles the concepts of routine and charisma from the point of view of place, and calls them familiarity and strangeness. He says that the existential structure of man is such “that we create familiarity around ourselves”⁸, unlike art which “is presented in contexts that create strangeness”⁹, and that the tendency of aesthetics is to “maximize strangeness and to minimize familiarity”¹⁰.

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Such view on familiarity and strangeness, otherwise called routine and charisma, is perfectly in line with Naukkarinen and Saito’s view. All three defend the importance of routine and not charisma. Saito distinguishes two ways in which we value everyday. The first approach is ‘normative’ approach, the search for extraordinary in the ordinary. The second approach is ‘descriptive’ approach, the approach that emphasizes the ordinary in the ordinary, the approach that Saito, through her efforts to emphasize the moral dimension of everyday aesthetics, takes.

However, if we consider everything discussed above, and not just aesthetic approach to everyday life, we quickly realize that a preference for one of the two possible modes

of operation is not the best way to go. Routine may be more calm and manageable than charisma is, but both play a crucial role in one's life. The question that arises is how to make routine charismatic and charisma routine-like.

Routine-charisma and charismatic-routine

In his book, Schiller showed that the dichotomy of human nature can only be resolved by the introduction of a third path, a unique bridge that does not only merge the properties of the two opposing drives, but goes beyond them. Doing so, he does not only resolve the dichotomy of human nature, but also points out a crucial view on the dichotomy in general, pointing out the role art plays in the formation and transformation of society and moral possibility.

Even Schopenhauer demonstrates the importance of art when it comes to change. According to him, art is the only way to stop the suffering, the only way to escape the Will. He thus recognizes two levels - beautiful and sublime. Beautiful and sublime are in the effect quite similar to their effect of routine and charisma. Of course, just as routine transitions to charisma and charisma to routine, so does beautiful transition to sublime and vice versa. The key question is how to make these transitions permanent, without preferring one over the other; how to permanently stop the suffering; or better yet, how to solve the dichotomy of aesthetics as Schiller solved the dichotomy of human nature.

It seems that only every individual for himself can find an answer to this, since the notion of routine and charisma differs from individual to individual. Still, the common ground all people have is a constant, deliberate interplay between routine and charisma. Schopenhauer showed that beautiful and sublime can stop the suffering, but it can be stopped ever so long before the Will catches up with us. In order to avoid this, it is necessary to continuously transition from routine to charisma and vice versa.

Aesthetic-ethical approach

Evolutionary aesthetics does not study the direct connection between art and change, and it certainly does not study the dichotomy of human nature. Nevertheless, it gives us the essential knowledge about the inseparability of human nature and aesthetics. Naukarinen wrote: "We cannot avoid producing aesthetic objects and events of some kind even if we ourselves don't always intend it or notice the outcome"¹¹, and the same goes for evolutionary aesthetics.

Precisely this aesthetic part, studied indirectly or directly, in relation to society or individual, is crucial for change. If we recall Fromm's words, change is possible only if it stems from the nature of man. One of the needs that stems from human nature, from aesthetic part of human nature, is the above mentioned and presented constant interplay between routine and charisma. This interplay thus forms the aesthetic part

of *aesthetic-ethical approach*.

The second part of the approach is the ethical part. The word ethical is used because both Schiller and Mandoki, Saito and Naukkarinen emphasize in their works the interweaving of aesthetics and moral. Of course, the question of interweaving aesthetics and moral is very broad and, like Naukkarinen says, study of this question is a field of study on its own, but what is essential is that by continuous interplay between routine and charisma we also act ethically.

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ENDNOTES

1. Immanuel Wallerstein, *World-system Analysis* (London: Duke University Press, 2004), 74
2. Ibid., 77
3. Immanuel Wallerstein, *Utopistics, Or, Historical Choices of the Twenty-first Century* (New York: The New Press, 1998), 90
4. Ossi Naukkarinen, "What is 'Everyday' in Everyday Aesthetics?," *Contemporary Aesthetics 2*, November 28, 2018, <https://www.contempaesthetics.org/newvolume/pages/>

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5. Ibid.

6. Ibid.

7. Ibid.

8. ArtoHaapala, "On the Aesthetics of the Everyday: Familiarity, Strangeness, and the Meaning of Place," in *The Aesthetics of Everyday Life* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2005), 40

9. Ibid., 51

10. Ibid., 52

11. OssiNaukkarinen, "What is 'Everyday' in Everyday Aesthetics?," *Contemporary Aesthetics* 2, November 28, 2018, <https://www.contempaesthetics.org/volume>

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